

Contribution of Rural Tourism Initiatives to the Local Community's Financial Capital Assets

Author Details: Caroline Chelangat

Moi university, school of Tourism, hospitality and event management, Department of tourism management.

Email address: carolinetoro2008@yahoo.com

Abstract

Rural tourism is a significant form of tourism which plays an important role and gives many benefits to rural areas community. In Mara Triangle Rural tourism has been in existence since the establishment of the Maasai Mara National Reserve (MMNR) in 1961 although limited studies have been done on its contribution to the local community livelihoods. Hence, this study was conducted in the Mara Triangle to establish community perspectives on the contribution of rural tourism initiatives to the local community's financial capital assets. Both descriptive and explanatory research designs were used. Questionnaires and focus group discussions were used to collect the primary data. The target population comprised of Mara conservancy staff, the staff of the tented camps i.e. Kichwa Tembo, Mara West and Little Governors and the local people living adjacent to the park up to 3 km away from the reserve boundary. 100 respondents were randomly selected for the survey and 18 respondents were purposively selected for focus group discussions. Three (3) focus group discussions, each comprising of 6 respondents were held while quantitative data was analyzed using both descriptive statistics and multiple regression and qualitative data was analyzed by the use of content analysis. The study findings revealed that rural tourism initiatives have significant positive contribution to financial capital asset ($P= 0.0000$). The findings further showed that rural tourism initiatives contributes to direct employment of the local community (Mean= 3.80 ± 0.10), provision of school bursaries (Mean= 3.65 ± 0.12), provision of training programs (Mean= 3.50 ± 0.12); community based projects (Mean= 3.45 ± 0.11) and support for local sport activities (Mean= 3.43 ± 0.11). The study concludes that rural tourism initiatives contribute significantly to financial capital assets of the local community. However, to sustain the contribution of rural tourism initiatives to the local community financial capital assets, there is need to promote community-based projects and enhanced more support on local sport activities.

Keys words: Rural tourism, Rural tourism initiatives, Financial capital assets

INTRODUCTION

About 75 per cent of the world's people live in rural areas (Holland *et al.*, 2003; Oketch *et al.*, 2012) besides top tourism destinations, particularly in developing countries. A majority of national parks, wilderness areas, mountains, lakes, and cultural sites are located in rural areas, thus making tourism an important attribute of the rural livelihood diversification in these areas. It is in this context that rural tourism is identified as a tool for rural revitalization (Oketch *et al.*, 2012). A significant question is whether more can be done to develop tourism within such rural areas, as a way of dispersing the benefits of tourism and increasing its poverty impact (Holland, *et al.*, 2003).

According to Holland *et al.* (2003) and Oketch *et al.* (2012), rural tourism takes many different forms and is pursued for different reasons. There are developmental reasons to promote tourism as an approach for regeneration in areas where there is agro-industrial collapse, or in diversification of a remote marginal agricultural area into adventure tourism or cultural tourism. Additionally, rural tourism preserves some depth to a world increasingly being flattened out by the forces of globalization (Tanahashi, 2010 as cited in Oketch *et al.*, 2012). Other reasons relate more to development of the tourism product such as diversifying a country's image, or alleviating bottlenecks in popular sites (Holland *et al.*, 2003).

Moreover Oketch *et al.*, 2012 argued that with decline in rural economies over the last three decades, it is possibly understandable that governments have given a great deal of attention to the economic benefits of tourism, mostly for rural areas attempting to keep step and adapt to the vital globalized economy. The

benefit of rural tourism is that it is based on local initiatives, local management, has local spin-offs, is rooted in local scenery and it taps into local culture and it can aid to generate local initiatives (Oketch *et al.*, 2012). Also, rural tourism is being used for socio-economic regeneration and diversification (Sharpley & Sharpley (1997).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Rural Tourism

Sillignakis (2001) suggests a tripartite definition of rural tourism – from a “geographic and demographic perspective”, a “product perspective”, and a “tourist experience perspective”. The geographic and demographic perspective describe rural tourism as a balanced activity which takes place in an environment outside the highly urbanized areas and which is characterized by small-scale tourism business set in areas where agricultural pursuits, forestry or natural areas dominate land use. This perspective seems to be prejudiced towards a general concern with the environment and the scale of business. Though it mentions the demographic aspect, it does not specify the role of rural tourism in changing the livelihoods of people. It is more engrossed on the geographic rather than the demographic aspect. The product related meaning views rural tourism as an activity whose product can be segmented to include rural attractions, rural adventure tours, nature-based tours, ecotourism tours, country towns, rural resorts, and country-style accommodation, together with festivals, events and agricultural education. The initial point in this perspective is difficult in that it does not match the product with its costs and benefits. It therefore isolates the product from the people who should derive benefit from it. Thus, the use of the product for rural tourism development and improvements in rural livelihoods is not clear in this perspective (Sillignakis, 2003).

From a tourist experience perspective, rural tourism is an activity which offers a different range of experiences to those offered in large cities and whose emphasis is on the tourist’s experience of the products and activities of the area (Sillignakis, 2003). Therefore, this perspective adopts a “tourist-centred” approach to rural tourism rather than a “provider-centred” approach. An approach of this nature disregards some of the harsh realities of most of the rural areas, especially in the developing world, where tourism is seen as a solution for job losses and rural depopulation.

Rural Tourism Initiatives

According to Tugba and Gulen (2012), rural tourism initiatives is a kind of rural activities and its characteristics is natural and humanistic. It comprises of customs, scenery, landscape (about local country and agricultural), and other attractions. Its forms of attractions are leisure, sightseeing, experience, and learning, and so on (Jingming & Lihua 2002; Deqian, 2006; Holland, *et al.*, 2003). Rural tourism initiatives or rurally located tourism can also include campsites, lodges, safari drives, craft markets, cultural displays, adventure sports, walking trails, heritage sites, musical events and any tourist activity-taking place in a rural area. (Jingming & Lihua, 2002). Similarly, according to Nilsson (2002), rural tourism is based on the rural environment in general while farm tourism is based on the farm and farmer. This means that within the context of rural tourism, farm tourism enterprises are more closely related than other tourism operations. However, Reid *et al.*, (2000) stated that rural tourism initiatives can be categorized into Agri-tourism which includes a variety of activities, services and amenities provided by farmers and rural people to entice tourists to their area in order to make additional income for their businesses and farm tourism. This form of tourism activity conducted in a rural farm area, may include tending to farm animals, planting, harvesting, and processing of farm products. The central activity is in the wider rural area (walking, boating) but the majority of visitors are accommodated on farms, either working farms or farms converted to accommodation facilities (Tugba & Gulen, 2012).

Contribution of Rural tourism to Financial Capital Assets

Rural tourism can contribute to financial capital asset in many ways. It includes: -

a) Creation of jobs

The development of rural tourism can create job opportunities through the establishment of tourist facilities such as camps, lodges and bed and breakfast and accommodation (Mbaiwa, 2003). The labor-intensive

nature of tourism facilitates the creation of employment in rural communities, particularly services and new product development. The creation of employment is critical to poverty alleviation and stabilization of the rural population. Rural tourism segment demands inputs such as foodstuffs and supporting services from other sectors of the economy and this means, it can generate new employment opportunities, especially among the low-skilled rural poor. Rural tourism linked with the agricultural sector is an advantage because this makes it a propeller of economic growth in rural development (McCarthy & Serju, 2006).

b) Balance of Payments

The balance of payments account is a record of economic transactions during a period of time (usually a year) between residents of the country in question and the rest of the world. According to Mathieson and Wall (1992), the income a country gains from tourism can help to balance the national balance of payments. It is considered important as the country then gains foreign or hard currency. Also as stated by Krause (2004), effects on the balance of payments are considered the most known economic impacts of tourism. It includes the value of all goods, gifts, loans, foreign aid and gold that comes in or leaves the country as well as the connections between these.

c) Generate income

According to Knowd (2001), a study of Victorian farm tourism showed that 78% of the farmers started tourism ventures for extra income. Half of those farms made close to 15% of their income from their tourism activities. Farms which had tourism as a companion industry had an average of 22% extra income. In a similar study in the north-west Sydney basin, 14% of farming businesses were involved in tourism and 72% of them were making close to 10% of their income from tourism (Knowd, 2001).

Tourism in rural areas is used by people from occupations other than farming to generate supplementary income. An examination of the hosts in rural areas along the Hortobagy in Eastern Hungary showed that occupants are not only attached to agriculture. They are employed in industry, services, and education, and some are pensioners and unemployed (Szabo, 2005). This protects the rural economy from the competitive job opportunities and higher salaries and wages provided by the urban areas. The direct and indirect effects of industrialization and commercialization of agriculture created a business risk for farmers. The advantage of business restructuring in favour of rural tourism is that farmers are not exposed to risk if the agricultural industry stagnates or becomes competitively unprofitable (Ashley, 2002).

d) Reduction of Poverty

Most rural areas have small populations compared to urban centers. Rural-urban migration can convert rural areas into demographic deserts where depopulation takes away hundreds of inhabitants (Collantes & Pinilla, 2004). Rural-urban migration can create a population structure that is characterized by a predominance of old people and children. Once this occurs most of the rural community structures and services become underutilized and businesses close down, which results in more unemployment and more poor individuals. This results in rural workers leaving with their labour, resulting in low productivity in agriculture (Omoniwa *et al.*, 2009). In order to control rural urban migration and retain young people in rural areas, governments, especially in developing countries, should pursue strategies such as tourism development, which offer opportunities for investment in rural infrastructure that can improve the development of non-farm rural economic activities.

Tourism is one of the possible means of dealing with both the first-round and second-round effects of urbanization by alleviating poverty and developing livelihoods, particularly in rural areas. Rural tourism can curb urbanization by creating new jobs, decrease migration, and help to maintain the local level of services (Komppula, 2007). In recent years, tourism has become an increasing phenomenon in rural areas, affecting the livelihoods of many of the rural poor.

a) Increase in the Standard of Living

Mansour and Mahin (2013) stated that due to numerous economic benefits of tourism and its potential growth it helps in the increase of standard of living of the people by offering new and better jobs, which in turn help them to improve the quality of life and their families.

Rogerson and Visser (2004) contend that tourism in rural areas contributes to the improvement of living standards of populations. Moreover, they argued that rural tourism encourages citizens to contribute in the local economy and take pride in their resources. Besides the persistent socio-economic needs of the local communities adjacent to the protected areas, the decision to invest in tourism reinforces the community's faith in tourism and recognition of the valuable contribution that tourism can play in community development and improvement of the lives of rural people (Rogerson & Visser, 2004). As tourism generates employment and additional income for rural families it results in social changes, associated social benefits, improvement of lives, alleviation of poverty, minimization of rural depopulation, facilitation of the transfer of new ideas from other parts of the world to rural areas, and the strengthening of the rural identity (Polucha & Zukovskis, 2010).

RESEARCH METHOD

The study was conducted as Mara triangle in Narok county. Descriptive and explanatory designs were used to generate the required information. The target population include Mara conservancy staff, the staff of the tented camps i.e. Kichwa Tembo, Mara West and Little Governors and the local people living adjacent to the reserve up to 3 km away from the reserve boundary. Simple random and purposive sampling technique was used to identify the respondents for this study. Questionnaires was used to collect the quantitative data, with Cronbach alpha being used to determine the reliability of the scale used and focused group discussion was used to collect qualitative data. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation and inferential statistics (regression analysis) to determine the relation between dependent variable to a set of independent variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contribution of rural tourism initiatives to different components of financial capital assets of the local community.

The study sought to assess the contribution of tourism initiatives to financial capital. Likert scale was used where: 5= strongly agree 4= agree 3= undecided 2= disagree 1= strongly disagree. The results in table 1 show that the local community have benefited from tourism through provision of employment (M=3.80; SD=0.985), provision of school bursaries (M=3.65; SD=1.185) and provision training programmes (M=3.50; SD=1.185). Some of the respondents were undecided whether it contributes to community-based projects (M=3.45; SD= 1.173) or it provide support for local sport activities. (M=3.43; SD=1.175).

Table 1 Contribution of rural tourism initiatives to different components of financial capital assets

	Mean	SD
Provision of school bursaries	3.65	1.185
Support for local sport activities	3.43	1.175
Provision of training programs	3.50	1.185
Provide employment	3.80	.985
Community based projects	3.45	1.173

Source: Field survey, 2017

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

The study adopted the regression model to examine how each rural tourism initiatives contribute to financial asset of the local community. The results are illustrated in table 2.

From table 2 the R² value of 92% showed that rural tourism initiatives contribute significantly to financial capital assets of local community. Also, the results show that cultural tours (P=0.002), community base projects (P=0.000), sale of souvenirs (P=0.000), cultural entertainment (P=0.016) and wildlife viewing (P=0.002) significantly contributes to financial capital assets of the local community in Mara Triangle. During FGD, participants reported that it contributes financial capital assets through generation of employment. Cultural manyattas (P=0.125) doesn't contribute much since it is rarely practiced by local community in Mara Triangle.

The regression equation will be;

$$Y_1 = 0.033 + 0.207 X_1 + 0.015 X_2 + 0.000 X_3 - 4.72 X_4 + 0.056 X_5 + 0.004 X_6 + \varepsilon$$

Table 2. Contribution of Rural Tourism initiatives to Financial Capital assets

Number of obs = 90

Prob> F = 0.0000

R-squared = 0.9225

Adj R-squared = 0.9216

Root MSE = 0.13793

Financial capital	Coef	Std. Err	T	P> t
Constant	0.0326334	0.0151032	2.16	0.031
Cultural tour	0.2079414	0.0678429	3.07	0.002
Community based projects	0.0154267	0.0003024	51.01	0.000
Sale of souvenir	0.0000233	3.20e-06	7.29	0.000
Cultural entertainment	-4.72e-08	1.95e-08	-2.42	0.016
Wildlife viewing	0.0558341	0.0183035	3.05	0.002
Cultural manyattas	0.0036624	0.002384	1.54	0.125

Source: Field Survey, 2017**DISCUSSION**

In terms of livelihoods, the results of the study in assessing the contribution of tourism initiatives to financial capital assets of the local community showed that the residents have benefited economically from tourism through provision of employment ($M=3.80$; $SD=0.985$) since some of the local community work in the camps, Mara conservancy and other are self-employed through the sale of souvenirs. Findings also indicate that the majority of the benefits are not direct from the development of tourism initiatives, but are indirect effects, resulting from donations, bursaries, among others, from the Mara conservancy through donors.

A study by McCarthy and Serju (2006) agrees with findings in that the labour-intensive nature of tourism facilitates the creation of employment in rural communities, particularly services and new product development. The creation of employment is critical to poverty alleviation and stabilization of the rural population. The rural tourism segment demands inputs such as foodstuffs and supporting services from other sectors of the economy and in this way, it can generate new employment opportunities, especially among the low-skilled rural poor. Its link with the agricultural sector is an advantage because this makes it a propeller of economic growth in rural development.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, based on findings, it is evident that rural tourism initiatives contribute to financial capital of the local community through generation of employment, provision of bursaries and community empowerment through training programmes. However, there is need to link with other initiatives sectors like agriculture since tourism alone will not be sufficient especially during low season. Moreover, while tourism contributes to diversifying livelihood strategies, they can also create new dependencies of the local communities.

RECOMMENDATION

In order for rural tourism to contribute more towards job opportunities, entrepreneurial skills and income generation, the study recommends that the Narok County government through Ministry of tourism and wildlife should strengthen partnerships with the local business sector, the local community sector and general stakeholders, as well as the policy-makers to ensure a faster integrated tourism development process.

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